

Methods of Educating and Developing Students Voice in Music Culture Classes

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Abstract

The article discusses how a music teacher organizes effective techniques in the process of listening to music, directs students to the development of personality, the formation of their musical worldview, as well as the comprehensive development of the personality of young people.

Keywords: listening to music, method, skill, art, music, culture, personality, musical literacy, elegance, artistic taste, national pride,

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Introduction: It is important to cultivate students' voices in music culture classes to develop a sense of vocal dynamics. At the same time, it is necessary to develop the ability of each performer to make his voice sound at a certain level, to hear and to hear the voices of other singers.

Pronunciation or diction also plays an important role in developing and nurturing students' voices. In a music culture class, it is important for the performers to understand the content of the song. At the same time, the work to be performed must reach the audience clearly. Therefore, students who sing in class are required to be able to pronounce the text clearly.

In elementary school, students need to learn to distinguish between melancholy, merry, marsh, dance, and fast and fluent songs. It is important that students gain an initial understanding of the length and pitch of sounds and begin to study note writing. Students will first develop an understanding of "high" and "low" sounds. The music teacher needs to draw the students' attention to the fact that the song is sometimes raised or lowered, and sometimes kept at the same level.

To do this, use the following method:

- Shows the volume by moving the teacher's hands up or down;
- A vowel is drawn in the form of a ladder to explain to students that the sounds in a song can be sung up or down one after the other.

Students should be introduced to the different lengths of sounds. Not all stretches rise at once. Elementary students are taught quarter and quarter notes that are common during singing. Because it is difficult for students to understand the names of "quarter" or "quarter" note lengths, these words can be interpreted conditionally as "long" and "short." In the first half of the year there will be preparatory classes for learning to write notes. In the second semester, students will be able to write notes from the first octave to the second octave and learn their meaning. They will also learn the keys of the violin (sol) and bass (fa). Five parallel note strings are displayed before the pitch and key symbols are displayed. The notes are written on and between these parallel lines, and, if necessary, five additional lines are drawn below and above the line of the note. Then the violin and bass keys are written on the note line.

After these exercises, a part of the speaker is sung according to the notes.

At the end of the school year, students begin to develop the skills of using notes and understanding and singing songs. They develop the ability to listen to and experience music. It is important to remember that all the basics of music education in the future begin in this elementary school, and the level of musical knowledge of students expands. Singing styles, such as singing to a note, singing a part of a vocal chord, and singing songs that include a vocal from the first octave to the second octave, will continue in the second grade. In the process of teaching songs, the names of the notes are said first, and then they are sung.

In music culture classes, students gain an understanding of the means of expression in music. The teacher should explain to the students the content, character, and variety of expressions of the songs sung in each music lesson.

In music lessons, the teacher informs the students about the mood. Students will first learn the simplest elements of the mode, and then their structure, composition, stages, and character. One of the simplest elements of Lad is whether a song is finished or not. The song then introduces the tonic, which plays an important role in the completion of the melody.

During practice, children should be asked if the song is complete. The teacher sings a familiar song to the students and does not stop until they reach the tonic. Students will need to determine if the song is complete. Then they all have to finish the tonic at the same time.

Students should be able to identify the percussion in the songs they are singing. To do this, one of the familiar songs is sung, and then the number of percussion sounds in them is determined. Indicates the style in which the percussion sounds are written in the notes. In addition to the above, they should continue to master the elements of solfeggio singing. To do this, students are taken from one of the songs they have learned and the notes are sung without words.

Many hours are devoted to mastering the means of expression of music in the elementary school curriculum, and skills in major and minor tones, intervals, scale, length, and their types will continue to be developed. Songs written in major and minor tones will be played, and major and minor trinities will be mastered. The content of songs performed in major and minor tones varies. Songs written in minor tones are calm and sad. The melodies, written in major tones, are lively and uplifting, highlighting all the elements of the tone.

To strengthen the ability to hear music, success is achieved in order to sing the trinities of major and minor, with a clear intonation of the third tone. Major and minor trio singing lessons help students master the tones and halftones provided for in the elementary school curriculum. When explaining intervals to students, sing familiar songs and point out that the jumps between major and minor sounds occur in different ways. It is necessary to determine the intervals of this type before singing and then. In addition, students will be introduced to hexadecimal notes, pauses, and their lengths.

Students will be introduced to the signs of alters - sharp and flat. There will be more music lessons and singing lessons based on the notes. Solfeggio exercises and songs often have to be sung directly to the note without preparation.

This type of exercise can help students develop their musical skills. In all other secondary schools, music literacy is required to be associated with singing at all times, without compromising performance skills.

The following results are achieved in cultivating students' voices in music culture classes. There are a number of issues that need to be addressed when working with primary school students, as well as some ways to develop and nurture voice. Warming up is very important in developing and nurturing students' voices in music lessons.

The warm-up is done at the beginning of the class. In addition, the adjustment of the sound serves to prepare the sound apparatus for work on the work. Sound heating gives good results in sound development if it is carried out according to the following requirements.

1. The vocal chorus exercises used to warm the voice should be appropriate to the students' vocal range.
2. When practicing singing, students should be able to sing freely in the lower and upper registers, and should not be allowed to sing with difficulty or difficulty.
3. Vocal and choral exercises should be done slowly and without haste.
4. Singing should not be mispronounced during singing exercises.
5. Exercises should be sung at medium pitch and should not be sung too loud or too low.
6. In the process of singing, attention should be paid to the quality and free singing of the performers.
7. Make sure that all sounds are sung at the same pitch.

The above requirements apply not only to the practice of singing, but also to the teaching of works. If special vocal and choral exercises are conducted on a regular basis based on these requirements, students' singing skills can be improved and the vocal apparatus can be developed from year to year. Vocal exercises or singings in a bottom-up or top-down movement are also helpful in developing students' voices in music lessons. Because these exercises develop and increase students' vocal range. In addition to vocal and choral

exercises, songs play an important role in developing and nurturing students' voices in music lessons.

Discussion: For elementary school students, it is important that the songs chosen by the teacher fit the vocal range of those performers. During a music lesson, there may be times when you need to play a complex song in a short amount of time. In such a situation, the teacher has to pass the lessons at a fast pace, relying on gifted students with musical abilities.

Students who are musically idle or unprepared do not have the ability to quickly master a song taught by a teacher. As a result, students may become tired and even suffer from voice disorders.

That is why it is important to plan your singing, sound development, upbringing, rehearsal time and time for each song according to its simplicity and complexity.

It is especially harmful to study complex works with primary school students. Also, the inclusion of works written for older performers in the curriculum of primary classes can lead to various diseases of the vocal apparatus. That is why it is important to teach elementary students moderately complex songs in the classroom, as well as artistic performance.

The development of musical awareness is also important in the musical education of students. The following should be considered when developing students' vocal skills in music lessons:

1. The teacher should constantly characterize the chorus in the classroom;
2. The teacher should carefully monitor and evaluate changes in the overall chorus sound;
3. Each student in the lesson should be trained to consciously feel their voice in the chorus.

Singing the work with clear pronunciation or diction ensures the freedom of the vocal apparatus.

Conclusion: In conclusion, music culture classes in secondary schools can be very effective if they are combined with activities such as music literacy and listening to music to develop students' voices and vocal dynamics. Skills such as singing correctly, cultivating and developing students' voices are achieved. Students' interest in music and their desire to sing will increase.

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